

THE BASIC BRANCHES OF LINGUISTICS

Raimov Lazizjon Alisherovich

Termiz University of Economics and Service

lazizjon_raimov@tues.uz

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the current types and trends of modern linguistics.

Linguistics, or linguistics, studies and analyzes the communication tool - language as a system - as a whole object, a complex social phenomenon. In the process, it comes in many forms. This is due to the nature of language, which has a social character, the need to study and study it from different angles, and the fact that this is absolutely true from a scientific point of view.

Linguistics is a powerful symbol of spirituality, which is reflected in the study of the language, which is the wealth of the nation, in the following ways:

1. Dynamic linguistics.
2. Static linguistics.
3. Synchronous linguistics.
4. Diachronous linguistics.
5. Intralinguistics.
6. Extralinguistics.
7. Paralinguistics.
8. Psycholinguistics.
9. Sociolinguistics.
10. Mathematical linguistics.
11. Computer Linguistics.
12. Cognitive linguistics.
13. Pragmalinguistics.
14. Linguoculturalology.

1. Dynamic linguistics. Dynamic linguistics mainly studies language in its real existence, in the active performance of various tasks in the communicative process, in “development” and change.

2. Static linguistics. Static linguistics distinguishes and describes a specific period (segment) of language activity that is fully synchronized.

3. Synchronous linguistics. Simultaneous linguistics is inextricably linked with static and structural linguistics and serves to describe the “stagnant” and “stable” state of a language in a given period.

4. Diachronous linguistics. Diachronous linguistics is inextricably linked with dynamic and atomistic linguistics, and studies the laws and consequences of the development of language and the development of language units.

5. Intralinguistics (internal linguistics). Internal linguistics studies the systematic relationship of language units, regardless of extralinguistic factors.

6. Extralinguistics (external linguistics). Foreign linguistics studies the development and function of language in relation to socio-political, socio-historical, ethnic, and geographical factors.

7. Paralinguistics. Paralinguistics is directly related to the activity of speech, the movement of hands and face (gestures, facial expressions), which is a constant companion of speech, which occurs simultaneously with the expression of ideas in the speech process, the height of speech, expressive- is an area that explores a number of aspects, such as emotional painting.

8. Psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics as a generalization (synthesis) of psychology and linguistics studies the speech process in terms of content, communicative significance, the orientation of the speech act to a specific socio-practical goal, and its relevance.

9. Sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics is a necessary and logical connection between the sciences of sociology and linguistics and deals with the relationship between society and language (language and society).

10. Mathematical linguistics. Mathematical linguistics examines the application of mathematical methods (eg, statistical

methods, information theory, etc.) in the study and description of language.

11. Computer Linguistics. Computer linguistics is a branch of applied linguistics whose main purpose is to solve linguistic problems by means of a computer, directly under its "guidance".

12. Cognitive linguistics. Cognitive linguistics is one of the newest branches of linguistics. This linguistics arose from the necessary interdependence of the sciences of cognitology and linguistics in order to work together.

13. Pragmalinguistics. Pragmatic linguistics is the result of a new stage of cognitive (empirical) research, research, formed on the basis of the achievements of structural linguistics. It takes as a system the state of use of the linguistic unit, the speech activity.

14. Linguoculturalology. Linguoculturalology was formed on the basis of linguistics, cultural studies.

In short, the science of linguistics as a whole, as noted, studies the language system through its various features, areas, with all its essence, complexity, with infinite communicative possibilities.

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